

Factors Influencing Environmental and Sanitation Conditions among a Rural Population in Bhagalpur District: A Cross-Sectional Study**Bhaskar Prasad Singh¹, Amrendra Narayan Chaudhary², Jolly³, Kamran Fazal⁴**¹Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur³Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur

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Abstract:**Introduction:** Overcrowding, poor sanitary conditions and open-air defecation are still major issues in rural households. This study aimed at assessing the internal, external environment and sanitation among a rural population.**Materials and Methods:** A cross-sectional survey was conducted in Bhagalpur District from June 2018 to August 2020. Around 379 households were assessed regarding environment and sanitation using a pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire.**Results:** Overcrowding was present in 29.1% houses. Twenty percent of the houses were inadequately ventilated. Separate toilet facilities were absent in 14.9% of houses. Mosquito nuisance was present among 29.9% houses and fly nuisance among 30.7% houses. Open drainage system was present among 21.3% of the houses. Lower socio-economic status was a significant risk factor for inadequate ventilation, absence of separate latrine and over-crowding.**Conclusion:** Awareness and health education on the health hazards of poor housing, imparting knowledge on government schemes such as Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana and Swachh Bharat are needed for those in the lower socio-economic strata for improving environment and sanitation.**Keywords:** Over-crowding, sanitation, open air defecation, Swachh Bharat.

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Introduction

We shall not defeat any of the infectious diseases that plague the developing world until we have also won the battle for safe drinking water, sanitation, and basic health care' – Kofi Annan [1]. Provision of clean environment and safe drinking water are essential components in health promotion and thus primary prevention of disease. Environmental sanitation is the 'management of human waste, excreta and drainage'. The United Nations-World Health Organization Joint Monitoring Programme for Water Supply and Sanitation defines 'improved' sanitation as: the means that hygienically separate human excreta from human contact and hence reduces health risks to humans [2]. Inadequate sanitation is thus the lack of improved facilities and hygienic practices that exposes people to human excreta and thus to disease-causing fecal-oral pathogens through different transmission pathways. Despite the advances in science and technology in the previous centuries, inequities in health have increased considerably. According to the Lixil Report published by the Oxford Economics, 'thousands of people die each day from lack of access to sanitary facilities. In addition to direct losses such as increased mortality

caused by lack of environmental sanitation, the indirect losses are estimated to be much more. They have estimated that 'the lack of access to sanitation has cost the world economy \$222.9 billion dollars in 2015. This amounts to 0.9% of the World's GDP' [3]. The economic loss is multi-dimensional in terms of increased mortality, loss of productive workforce, increased burden on health care and consequences of limited access to sanitation facilities. The brunt of the losses is borne by the Asian-Pacific countries such as India. Almost half of the world's economic losses due to poor sanitation occur in India, where \$106.7 billion doll losses occurred in 2015 [4]. Here, the economic losses due to lack of environmental sanitation is estimated to be at 5.2% of National GDP [5]. The rural households with the lower socio-economic status are affected the most by the economic losses. Diarrheal diseases and acute lower respiratory infections are very high causing increased mortality and morbidity. Over-crowding, inadequate ventilation, lack of access to safe drinking water and toilet facilities are still major issues in rural households. In the Millennium Developmental Goals, the goal for environmental sanitation fell

short by the greatest margin. Hence, if we are to achieve equitable sanitation as per the Sustainable Developmental Goals, there is a huge gulf to be covered.

Material and Methods

A cross sectional study was conducted among 379 families residing in Bhagalpur, District. Data collection was done over a period of 2 months from June 2018 to August 2020. According to the report published by WaterAid, titled Out of Order: The State of the World's Toilets 2017, 56% of the population in India have inadequate toilet facilities⁶. Hence, with a prevalence of 56%, 5% absolute precision and 95% confidence limits, the sample size is estimated to be 379 according to Open Epi. A house-to-house survey was conducted. A pre-tested, semi-structured questionnaire was interviewer was administered by the interviewer in the local language to the head of the family after obtaining informed written consent. The questionnaire contained data pertaining to socio-demographic variables such as age, gender, family members, type of family, materials of roof, walls, floor, cooking fuel used, presence of separate bathroom, toilet facilities, collection of waste, methods of garbage disposal and socio-economic status. Modified B.G Prasad Scale was used to classify socio-economic status of the

families. The income ranges were calculated by using Consumer Price Index for Industrial Workers as 287.

Data Entry and Analysis

The collected data was entered using MS Excel and analysed using SPSS v.23.0. Data was presented using tables and figures. Numerical data was summarized using means with standard deviations and median with interquartile ranges. Categorical data was presented using percentages. Chi square was used to compare proportions between different groups. P value of less than 0.05 was considered to be statistically significant.

Results

The socio-demographic details of the study population are mentioned in Table 1. As shown in the table 1, majority of the study population belong to Hindu religion. Nuclear family system is prevalent in almost two-third of the study population. Almost a third of the study population have more than 4 family members living in their house. When the study population was stratified based on their socio-economic status, most of the study population belonged to either upper, upper-middle or middle socio-economic classes.

Table 1: Socio-demographic variables

Variables	Mean± SD, n(%)
Religion	
Hindu	330(87.1)
Muslim	41(10.8)
Christian	8(2.1)
Family type	
Extended	47(12.4)
Nuclear	247(65.2)
Joint	70(18.5)
Three generation	15(3.9)
No. of family members	
<= 4	257(67.8)
>4	122(32.2)
Average house area (sq.ft)	1343±946.98
Family income (in Rs.)	16716±18116.95
Per capita income (in Rs.)	4489.19±4327.49
Socio-economic class	
Upper	95(25)
Upper middle	98(25.8)
Middle	91(24.01)
Upper lower	65(17.1)
Lower	30(7.9)

The detail of housing is given in table 2. Pucca houses with concrete roof, plastered brick wall and cemented floors are present in most of the houses.

Table 2: Details of housing

Housing details	Mean± SD, n(%)
House type	
Pucca	242(63.8)
Semi-pucca	91(24.01)
Kachhca	46(12.1)
Roof	
Concrete	279(73.6)
Thatched	61(16.1)
Tiled	39(10.3)
Wall	
Brick with plaster	271(71.5)
Brick	91(24.01)
Mud	17(4.5)
Floor	
Cemented	310(81.8)
Brick	22(5.8)
Mud	24(6.3)
Marble	22(5.8)
House area (sq.ft)	1303.16±960.59

Overcrowding was present in 29.1% of the houses. Almost one-fifth of the houses (20%) were inadequately ventilated. With regards to sanitation, 14.9% of the houses did not have a separate latrine. Members of the household practiced open air defecation. Among the houses which had separate latrines, cleanliness was found to be inadequate among 21.1% of the houses. The houses which did not have separate bathrooms had temporary sheds which were utilized by most women of the household. When the external environment was assessed, among the houses which had cattle, 53.2% of the households had attached cattle sheds. Among the remaining houses which had cattle sheds, the cattle shed was found to be located at less than 25 ft distance among 45% of the houses. There was mosquito nuisance and fly nuisance among 29.9% and 30.7% of the houses respectively. Rodent nuisance was reported among 61.9% of the houses.

Discussion

A total population of 5862, with 3008 males and 2854 females. The per capita income/ year according to the census data was Rs. 53,504. In the current study, the yearly per capita income was Rs. 53,870.28 which is comparable to the census data. According to census data [7], 91.79% of the population in Bhagalpur district is Hindu which is slightly higher compared to the 87.1% in the present study. But this is in concordance with the State data of 94.9% Hindus according to NFHS – 4 [8]. Around 3.87% of the population in Bhagalpur. Muslim which is much less compared to the 10.8% in the present study [7]. according to census data and the present study is 4% and 2.1% respectively. has a higher population of Muslims compared to the district average. As per the statistics of NFHS-4 data [8], 64.3% of the population belong to nuclear

families. This is in concordance with the present study, where 65.2% hail from nuclear families. With regards to housing, as per the data from NFHS-4 study, 72.1% of the people live in a pucca house and 20.5% live in a semi-pucca house. This is not in concordance with the present study where only 63.8% of the population resides in a pucca house and 24.01% reside in a semi-pucca house.

According to the study by Patwa and Pandit [9], with the launch of Swachh Bharat Mission, only 8.41% of the rural population in their study area in Bhagalpur village practiced open defecation. This is lesser compared to the 14.9% reported in the present study. Despite the presence of household toilets, rural areas still practice open defecation. This is indicated in the study by Yoganath and Bhatnagar [10], where 54.8% of the rural households in Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu still defecate in the open despite the presence of household toilets. In the present study, 13.10% of the households did not have a separate bathroom, which is much lesser than the report of 65th round of NSSO11 where 55% of the rural households did not have a separate bathroom. In the current study, 53.2% of the households had attached cattle sheds which was much higher compared to the 12.9% reported by NSSO 65th round [11]. Hence, rural households in the present study have inadequate sanitation and personal hygiene due to contamination of houses by the urine and excreta of cattle. In addition, this is an additional risk factor for increased fly nuisance reported by the households. Almost 27% of the households in Tamil Nadu have non-LPG fuel for cooking according to NFHS-4 [8], which is much higher than the 2.9% reported in the present study. According to NFHS-4 [8], 22.8% of the households in rural areas do not have a separate kitchen. This is slightly higher compared to the present study, where 19.52% of the households do not have a separate

kitchen making them vulnerable to indoor air pollution. In the present study, 20% of the households were inadequately ventilated which is lesser compared to the 26.8% reported in the 65th round of NSSO housing survey [11].

The NFHS-4 data states that, 12.7% of the population in Tamil Nadu utilize an insanitary water source for drinking water which is comparable to the 13.72% reported in the present study⁸. In the present study, 21.63% of the households had open drainage. This is much lesser than the report by NSSO 65th round¹¹, where 31% of the rural households had open drainage. This indicates the increased risk of rural households for food and water borne diseases. With respect to the determinants of environment and sanitation socio-economic status was inversely correlated with over-crowding in the present study. This is similar to the study by Pelissari et al [12], where low socio-economic status was associated with overcrowding. Over-crowding is further associated with the risk of developing infectious diseases such as tuberculosis [12], increased childhood accidents [13], poor psychological well-being [14] and domestic violence [15]. Inadequate ventilation is also a risk factor for respiratory diseases such as tuberculosis, influenza, vector borne diseases such as dengue. Improving natural ventilation has been shown to reduce the risk of pulmonary illnesses up to 20% [16]. Inadequate sanitation, present among low socio-economic households has been shown to be responsible for 1.5% of the global disease burden, 58% of the diarrheal illnesses and 5.5% of the preventable deaths among children under 5 years of age [17].

Conclusion

The findings of the present study indicate rural populations survive under a heavy burden of a web of interrelated factors ranging from overcrowding and poor housing facilities to inadequate water and sanitation and poor awareness about cleanliness. A strong grass-roots level, community-led program to impart health education, increase awareness and monitor progress is needed focusing on rural households. Information on Government schemes for housing such as Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana and Swachh Bharat Mission for constructing toilets should be made available to the rural population. Focus should be paid in imparting information on availing and utilization of these schemes in particular.

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